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Leveraging climate resilience capacities by (un)learning from transdisciplinary research projects

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ABSTRACT

Climate adaptation in Europe faces a significant implementation gap: while high-level policies set ambitious resilience goals, local knowledge integration and policy uptake remain slow due to entrenched institutional routines. Reflecting on lessons from three transdisciplinary European projects, this article aims to provide a fresh perspective on how climate resilience can be effectively enhanced through projects that facilitate institutional (un)learning. We tailor a climate resilience capacities framework to diagnose stewarding, unlocking, transforming and orchestrating capacities that enable coordinated shifts from risk-averse to risk-embracing adaptation. These capacities emerge from, and generate, processes that actively dismantle obsolete learnings while fostering novel, resilience-oriented behaviors and routines. Key examples include climate resilience pathways and the empowerment of champions and institutional entrepreneurs, an integrated approach and neutral facilitation and the formation of networks such as Communities of Practice and Real-World Labs. We propose that, while already successful ex-post, embedding this thinking at the conceptualization phase can further accelerate the transition to adaptive societies capable of embracing uncertainty and enhancing climate resilience.

1. Introduction

The first European Climate Risk Assessment (EEA, 2024) highlights accelerating compound climate crises across Europe exemplified by the 2021 floods and droughts in Germany, Belgium, and the Netherlands (Pedde et al., 2024). These crises result from complex interactions between environmental hazards and societal factors (Shah et al., 2020; Biesbroek et al., 2013) and are exacerbated by the possibility of worst-case scenarios (Kemp et al., 2022; Pedde et al., 2024). While high-level climate adaptation policies in Europe, such as the European Green Deal (EC, 2019) and National Adaptation Plans (NAPs) (EEA, 2022) acknowledge these risks, structural barriers, that is short-term reactive measures and entrenched behaviors, continue to hinder meaningful progress towards

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substantial climate resilience (Mattern et al., 2018; Fisk et al., 2023). Despite the “age of implementation” (Klein et al., 2017) with potential to enable radical transformation (Arteaga et al., 2023), Europe remains insufficiently prepared for escalating climate risk (EEA, 2024).

In this context, climate resilience policies will not be effective by themselves. Effective adaptation demands a paradigm shift in governance, involving both the acquisition of new tools and practices while actively unlearning “obsolescent learnings” (Adam et al., 2020), such as obsolete managerial governance logics that easily crowd out effective and transformative climate action (Deubelli and Mechler, 2021; Mattern et al., 2018). Thus, we concur that policies that reflect systemic and radical shifts are necessary to enhance climate resilience (Tàbara et al., 2018; Fedele et al., 2019; Lonsdale et al., 2015).

Unlearning outdated mental models, rather than adjusting within existing frameworks, is essential to bridge the implementation gap (Klammer et al., 2024). Unlearning involves *break-down processes* to facilitate the adoption of fundamentally new ways of thinking and acting that align with sustainability transitions (Van Oers et al., 2023). Transforming towards climate resilient systems requires *desirable* build-up and break-down processes typical of transitions (Fig. 1).

Acknowledging the role of bottom-up capacities in driving societal transformation (Thaler et al., 2019), European and national research funding channels, such as the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (Rayner 2023), are designed to support bottom-up learning from practice (Horcea-Milcu et al., 2024). Inter- and transdisciplinary projects, focused on Nature-based Solutions (Collier et al., 2023; Croeser et al., 2021), climate services (Daniels et al., 2020; McCullagh et al., 2024a), and climate-resilient infrastructure (Lückerath et al., 2020) provide societal impact (Belcher et al., 2019; Colloff et al., 2021) and knowledge to bridge between policy ambitions and practice (Currie-Alder and De Souza 2022; Hölscher et al., 2023). Knowledge exchange platforms are financed such as the European Climate Adaptation Platform Climate-ADAPT (Climate-ADAPT, 2024) and WeAdapt¹. Despite these initiatives and knowledge, emerging since landmark studies on science-policy-practice processes (Lang et al. 2012) and diagnostic tools to barriers to climate change adaptation (Moser and Ekstrom, 2010), the societal impact—defined here as meaningful changes in governance, behavior, and policy frameworks resulting from climate resilience actions—of local successes is still limited by institutional inertia. We argue that improving how climate resilience capacities are generated, beginning at the conceptualization and design phase of the projects, is critical to enhance scalability and transferability of valuable lessons while translating general resilience principles into practice and policy (Al Sayah et al., 2022; Daniels et al., 2020).

We propose that using frameworks, such as the transformative governance capacities (TGC) framework (Hölscher et al., 2019, 2020), provide the building blocks to diagnose institutional (un)learning (Oberlack et al., 2019, Pedde et al., 2019 a, b). Drawing from three transdisciplinary adaptation projects such as Catchment Strategies Towards Resilience (CASTOR, 2019), Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TALX, 2023, McCullagh et al., 2023) and Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events (DIRECTED,

Fig. 1. Knowledge structures like systems, routines and beliefs result from knowledge construction which influence behavior and vice versa. Transitions typically require unlearning and re-learning via break-down of knowledge and belief systems to influence behavior and build up new knowledge, in turn influencing behavior via adapted values and norms to transform systems, routines and habits (based on Klammer et al. (2024) and Krauss (2019)).

Schröter et al., 2024) we demonstrate how climate resilience capacities enable a shift away from maladaptive practices like risk-avoidance and overreliance on hard-engineering solutions to risk-embracing strategies that underpin climate resilience (represented by the orange arrow in Fig. 2). These capacities—stewarding, unlocking, transforming and orchestrating—operationalize resilience thinking for decision-makers. They provide a normative orientation for the type of institutional learning and unlearning that we propose, that is building up combinations of desirable enabling conditions locally, while breaking-down undesirable ones (Loorbach et al., 2017; Hebinck et al., 2022) through transformation-oriented pathways (Werners et al., 2021).

In all three projects, scientists acted both as knowledge holders and knowledge brokers. All three projects operate at local European scales and started with similar timing and time frames (3–5-year projects, starting between 2020 and 2022 and at least partly connected to previously funded projects). While local stakeholders are usually best placed to improve quality of decision-making in their adaptation context (Colloff et al., 2021; Brullo et al., 2024), scientists are challenged to rethink their own role and also act as knowledge brokers (Vinke- de Kruijf et al., 2022) or integration experts (Hoffmann et al. 2022) to ensure the effective alignment of information required for policy and practice (Gluckman et al., 2021; Hering, 2016).

2. Defining climate resilience capacities as the building blocks of institutional learning and unlearning

Climate resilience capacities emerge from institutional (un)learning processes, which are induced by and require changes in contextual variables (Moser and Ekstrom, 2010). The processes by which they emerge, and the resulting changes, are influenced by attributes of physical resources and the knowledge, skills and resources of actors but also rules and procedures (institutions) and impacts of events (for example, a prolonged drought) (Ostrom, 2009; Oberlack, 2017). Activities and processes in the projects form the “how” (Andrews et al., 2024). The actors’ capacities are diagnosed at the “operational level” (specific action-situations and place-based action at the level of stakeholder activities) to – and in in the context of – the “collective choice level” (policy, legislation, rules) (Ostrom, 2011). The emerging institutional (un)learning both generates and is reinforced by climate resilience capacities. The capacities form the building blocks (the “what”) of continued institutional adaptation, beyond the single projects and their lifetime (Table 1, right-hand side).

3. Climate resilience capacities as diagnostic building blocks emerging from transdisciplinary adaptation projects

We illustrate this thinking in practice, both at the collective choice and the operational levels. At the collective choice level, the projects operate in the context of European policy frameworks and funding mechanisms targeted at leveraging effective multi-level, transnational collaboration and polycentric governance (Jordan et al., 2015). At the operational level, similar to other local adaptation projects (Brullo et al., 2024), they produce knowledge through participation to collaborate (Berkes, 2017; Cinner and Adger, 2018). Accordingly, they all develop networks and experimental methods from existing communities, with the ambition to embed more effectively the emergence of knowledge and innovations, while supporting ongoing planning and implementation designed at higher-

Fig. 2. Closing the implementation gap means enabling capacities for institutional (un)learning for actors to coordinate across levels (from local, to regional, national, to European) and readapt. Capacities can emerge from agent interaction in adaptation planning at local levels and practice. It requires a continuous translation between governance levels towards a mindset shift from risk aversion to acceptance of unknowns through setbacks in the learning process. Figure inspired from CASTOR project.

Table 1

Climate resilience capacities in practice: (un)learning for transformative change as observed in three climate adaptation transdisciplinary projects. Description of project processes and activities and additional references to climate resilience capacities in Supplementary Material II and III.

Climate Resilience Capacity (Hölscher et al., 2019, 2020)	Relevant project processes and activities (operational level): how	Changes in context (collective choice level): what
Stewarding capacity	Climate resilient pathways approach (CASTOR), Champions as stewards (TALX) and Real-World Lab (DIRECTED). Integration of local knowledge in adaptation planning (all projects)	Learning to embrace uncertainty by empowerment, knowledge sharing and leadership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Champions and leaders facilitating self-re-organisation (Olsson et al., 2004) • Enhancing data, model, and Information interoperability to support communication and decision-making for managing disasters and adapting to climate change. Training and knowledge sharing and co- production (Norström et al., 2020) • Using climate resilient pathways approach to anticipate, adapt, cope, and recover (Haasnoot et al., 2013, Werners et al., 2021, Sparkes et al., 2023)
Unlocking capacity	Omgevingswet ^[1] as framing (CASTOR), neutral facilitation role to overcome national barriers (TALX), identifying funding and legislative gaps (DIRECTED). Mediation of interests through local networks (all projects)	Learning to recognize maladaptive practices and lock-ins to overcome them <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of unsustainable practices and institutional lock-ins through definition and identification of basin of attraction, such (un)sustainable land-use and policies (Eisenack et al., 2014) • Identification of governance barriers and use of partnerships and networks to address these (Biesbroek et al., 2015, Cinner et al., 2018) • Multi-stakeholder engagement to address power and interest relations (Vinke de-Kruijf et al., 2022)
Transforming capacity	Living Labs, Community of Practice (CASTOR), Partnerships (TALX) and Real-World Labs (DIRECTED). Innovation through resource channeling and embedding (all projects)	Learning how to stimulate Living Labs, Real World Labs as a safe space for innovation and how to nurture them after the projects end. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Aim of) institutionalization of Living Labs to facilitate continued multi-stakeholder collaboration, knowledge exchange, experimentation, and innovation (Tàbara et al., 2018) • Experimentation approach embedded in governance • Facilitating social learning Through multi-stakeholder • Knowledge co-production Processes to co-explore solutions (El Amiri et al., 2020)
Orchestrating capacity (key mechanisms across stewarding, unlocking, and transforming)	Community of Practice and Theory of Change (CASTOR), place-based approach to achieving long-term goals (TALX) and liaisons (DIRECTED), Climate resilience framework and liaisons roles as part a polycentric governance system (coordination emerging from all capacities)	Learning to coordinate action through polycentric governance mechanisms. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive development of long-term, shared goals • Dedicated 'liaison' roles to support multi-stakeholder collaboration, partnership, and network buildings to integrate innovations and knowledge into policy and practice, beyond the project life (Butler et al., 2022, Vinke- de Kruijf et al., 2022) • Designing shared goals and a change in the way climate governance is organized (Wiek and Iwaniec 2014; Belcher et al., 2019) • Practical and flexible frameworks emerge and are applied and updated from practice to maintain reversibility. In turn, a specific framework coordinates exchange through partnerships in community of practices (Wise et al., 2016)

^[1] The Omgevingswet is the Dutch Environment and Planning Act for an integrated approach of spatial planning, housing, infrastructure, the environment, nature and water.

level decision-making (national and European levels) (Brullo et al., 2024). Table 1 summarizes the four climate resilience capacities emerging from practice in the projects, which form the building blocks for institutional (un)learning: stewarding, unlocking, transforming and orchestrating. The three projects' selected outputs and outcomes, relevant to the diagnosis of capacities they generate, are described in detail in Supplementary Material II and III.

3.1. Stewarding capacity

Stewarding capacity is the ability to anticipate, cope and prepare in the context of deep uncertainty and extreme climate change

impacts. At the operational level, the projects mobilize knowledge largely through scenario analysis and knowledge sharing. Community-based champions are identified to provide leadership in climate adaptation planning (Olsson et al., 2004). Qualitative knowledge production methods include interviews, workshops and learning sessions (e.g., Sparkes et al., 2023). CASTOR and DIRECTED also build from quantitative evidence: hydrological modelling, with catchment databases and models shared with research institutes and waterboards and climatic hazard and risk modelling. In DIRECTED, Real-World Labs (RWLs) hosts are trained to lead their own process to integrate and co-produce knowledge among stakeholders to better understand and manage complex risks collaboratively, an approach which supports adaptive planning (Haasnoot et al., 2013; Werners et al., 2021).

3.2. Unlocking capacity

Unlocking capacity emerges when actors are able to eliminate the structural drivers and root causes of vulnerabilities to climate change and maladaptation. Through intermediation, knowledge co-production processes at the operational level support conflicting interests (Vinke-de Kruijf et al., 2022). This includes knowledge generation from different sectors, disciplines and levels (Norström et al., 2020) by effectively engaging scientists and stakeholders to address diverse needs, interests, power hierarchies, and beliefs (Meharg, 2023; Gluckman et al., 2021). These processes are facilitated by Community of Practices (CoP), partnerships, and RWLs (CASTOR, TALX, DIRECTED respectively) which also foster transforming capacity. Despite these similarities, the projects' rules and institutions to support unlocking capacity at the collective choice level are diverse (Supplementary Material II).

3.3. Transforming capacity

Transforming capacity emerges when space for innovation and experimentation is fostered and embedded in existing structures. In all projects, this space is created at the operational level through informal networks, such as CoPs, regularly gathering to discuss relevant topics, decision-making processes and facilitation of solutions and emerging business models, facilitated rather than steered, by research institutes (in CASTOR and TALX). The informal networks foster innovation by learning from and for practice (Wenger-Trayner et al., 2023). By design, at the collective choice level, the three projects have a high proportion of funding to maintain and further develop broad networks both in terms of multiscale institutional levels (from municipalities to waterboards, to provincial and national governments) and expertise in multiple disciplines. Networks of research organizations, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO's) and civil society organizations are built and maintained through multiple connected projects over time (El Amiri et al., 2020), such as the case with TALX, DIRECTED and CASTOR and the future climate resilience projects and networks they ignite.

3.4. Orchestrating capacity

Orchestrating capacity addresses the need to coordinate across sectors, governance levels and societal groups to foster synergies and mitigate trade-offs, by facilitating alignment towards long-term systemic goals, and mediation of interests. Theoretical and practical frameworks, such as the Theory of Change approach in CASTOR, provide a direction and a long-term vision approach. Innovation is coordinated through collaborative actors in networks, such as CoPs, partnerships and RWLs. CoPs support agenda-setting and are particularly useful to facilitate action in the context of multi-use spatial planning among competing interests (Steins et al., 2021).

4. Operationalizing institutional (un)learning from practice to address the implementation gap

Overlaps in outcomes (the “what”) of the different adaptation contexts, align with findings in local adaptation efforts' literature (see also Supplementary Material II and III and Table 1, and recent review by Brullo et al., 2024). Namely, enablers of adaptation tend to be most active, locally, at the operational level and barriers tend to be institutional in nature or connected to lack of political will or resources (Owen, 2020). We show that climate resilience capacities organize how to coordinate across levels without deprioritizing adaptation in its context, thus complementing studies on effectiveness and evaluation of progress in climate adaptation (see, for example, detailed analyses in Thaler et al., 2019). Climate resilience capacities highlight where actors have agency to foster institutional (un)learning as explained in Supplementary Material III. In the projects, examples are incentives for Community of Practice and Real-World Labs to continue and expand after the projects' completion (Supplementary Material III). While these examples apply to these specific projects, similarities to the Theory of Change as for example in Butler and colleagues (Butler et al., 2022), include leveraging climate resilience capacities enabling scientists to simultaneously focus on outcomes and impacts at the local level and strengthen delivery of knowledge beyond the scope of the projects. Pursuing this line of research in the future will be pivotal to support more rapid resilience capacity building and close the implementation gap to address the climate crisis.

Scientists can use climate resilience capacities as building blocks to characterize institutional (un)learning from practice, and address coordination and implementation gaps across scales. Doing so can avoid the temptation of the functionalist “trap” of understanding adaptation solely as response-oriented to physical or institutional barriers (Biesbroek et al., 2015), and instead focus on the lack of coordination between institutions (regional, national and, in the European case, European governmental bodies) and local communities' actively involved in projects (Petzold et al., 2023). Seeking consensus on the “myriad” ways to define climate adaptation goals, ranging from increasing adaptive capacities and resilience, enhancing governance and reducing vulnerabilities at a general level may be impossible, with conceptualization being operational in the context (Owen, 2020; Piemontese et al., 2022). Climate resilience capacities, as an intermediate level of abstraction, facilitate conceptualization between generic goals (explainable

through causality but prescriptive and, potentially, reductionist) and specific metrics (relevant in-depth, but within the scope of the project) (Oberlack et al., 2019; Eisenack et al., 2019). Our insights on institutional (un)learning are therefore susceptible to vary with different projects, a desirable attribute for progress in (local) adaptation. At higher levels, climate resilience capacities organize patterns of transformational change across local contexts, tailoring learning on how to embrace uncertainty in society and continue to move forward, as highlighted in Table 1. (Colloff et al., 2021; Nightingale et al., 2022; Fedele et al., 2019; Blythe et al., 2018, McCullagh et al., 2024b).

Is this intermediate level sufficient to address the implementation gap? The attributes of the framework provide the means to navigate the complexity of transition, transformation, and resilience thinking (Supplementary Material III). It also provides the substance to enable and accelerate uptake of locally relevant knowledge from stakeholder-driven research questions within the broader scientific theories (Piemontese et al., 2022). CASTOR, TALX and DIRECTED exemplify the many European transdisciplinary climate adaptation projects rooted in practice, not least those shared in knowledge exchange platforms, aiming to deliver impact pathways (Belcher et al., 2019) designed for adaptation and resilience. While the projects' impacts can be tested (monitoring and evaluation) only in the long-term, climate resilience capacities can foster the ability to influence adaptation practices transcending the projects (Tàbara et al., 2018). This is even true for projects, such as those exemplified here, which were not deliberately designed to develop climate resilience capacities.

5. Conclusions

There is an implementation gap between high level climate adaptation policies, adaptation practices and knowledge production. Overcoming this gap requires a transition to climate resilience which entails learning to embrace uncertainty and risk. Institutional (un)learning for such transitions consists of navigating away from consolidated practices through break-down and build-up processes. While resilience can, sometimes, be framed as a way to maintain the status quo under the guise of adaptation (Blythe et al., 2018), climate resilience capacities provide a useful diagnostic lens that recognizes and addresses the latent risks of transformations such as inadvertently preserving current maladaptive structures.

Although the projects did not explicitly set out to invest in building climate resilience capacities, they emerged organically through the projects' activities. CASTOR, TALX, and DIRECTED demonstrated that integrating facilitation efforts—such as mediation, neutral facilitation, and shared leadership models—was essential for breaking down structural barriers. These projects naturally fostered local networks, such as Communities of Practice, partnerships, and Real-World Labs, which helped build adaptive values, systems, and routines. By prioritizing inclusive, bottom-up processes, they mitigated the risk of marginalizing certain groups, while dedicated liaisons and climate resilience pathways empowered local actors and institutions to manage uncertainty through knowledge-sharing and leadership.

While investing directly in risk-embracing climate resilience capacities at the conceptualization stage of adaptation planning may still appear time-consuming by today's metrics, the benefits—whether near or long term—can outweigh the costs of waiting to explore and quantify the impacts of the next “fat-tail” surprises (Kemp et al., 2022). The lessons from CASTOR, TALX, and DIRECTED demonstrate how such capacities can emerge as part of a broader strategy to integrate innovations and broker knowledge. Designing and conceptualizing research projects with climate resilience capacities in mind might counteract the persistence of (de facto) response-focused climate adaptation with the new mindset to set resources for embedding innovation ultimately closing the implementation gap.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Simona Pedde: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Reginald Grendelman:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lydia Cumiskey:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Denise McCullagh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Joanne Vinke-de Kruijf:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Katharina Hölscher:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- Adam, R., Whitehouse, H., Stevenson, R.B., Chigeza, P. (2020). The Socioecological (Un)learner: Unlearning Binary Oppositions and the Wicked Problems of the Anthropocene. In: Cutter-Mackenzie-Knowles, A., Lasczik, A., Wilks, J., Logan, M., Turner, A., Boyd, W. (eds) Touchstones for Deterritorializing Socioecological Learning. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-12212-6_3.
- Al Sayah, M.J., Versini, P.-A., Schertzer, D., 2022. H2020 projects and EU research needs for nature-based adaptation solutions. *Urban. Clim.* 44, 101229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2022.101229>.
- Andrews, L.M., Munaretto, S., Mees, H.L., Driessen, P.P., 2024. Conceptualising boundary work activities to enhance credible, salient and legitimate knowledge in sustainability transdisciplinary research projects. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 155, 103722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103722>.
- Arteaga, E., Nalau, J., Biesbroek, R., Howes, M., 2023. Unpacking the theory-practice gap in climate adaptation. *Clim. Risk. Manag.* 42, 100567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2023.100567>.
- Belcher, B.M., Claus, R., Davel, R., Ramirez, L.F., 2019. Linking transdisciplinary research characteristics and quality to effectiveness: A comparative analysis of five research-for-development projects. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 101, 192–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.08.013>.
- Berkes, F., 2017. 'Environmental governance for the anthropocene? Social-ecological systems. Resilience. Collaborat. Learn., Sustain. 9 (7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9071232>.
- Biesbroek, R., Dupuis, J., Jordan, A., et al., 2015. (2015) Opening up the black box of adaptation decision-making. *Nature. Clim. Change* 5, 493–494. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2615>.
- Biesbroek, G.R., Klostermann, J.E.M., Termeer, C.J.A.M., et al., 2013. On the nature of barriers to climate change adaptation. *Reg. Environ. Change* 13, 1119–1129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-013-0421-y>.
- Blythe, J., Silver, J., Evans, L., Armitage, D., Bennett, N.J., Moore, M.L., Brown, K., 2018. The dark side of transformation: latent risks in contemporary sustainability discourse. *Antipode* 50 (5), 12061223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12405>.
- Brullo, T., Barnett, J., Waters, E., et al., 2024. The enablers of adaptation: A systematic review. *Npj Clim. Action* 3, 40. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-024-00128-y>.
- Butler, J.R.A., Wise, R.M., Meharg, S., Peterson, N., Bohensky, E.L., Lipsett-Moore, G., Dunstan, P., 2022. 'Walking along with development': climate resilient pathways for political resource curses. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 128, 228–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.11.020>.
- CASTOR (2019). CATCHMENT STRATEGIES TOWARDS RESILIENCE: DUTCH PLEISTOCENE LANDSCAPES IN THE ANTHROPOCENE. <https://www.nwo.nl/en/cases/sandy-landscape-balance>. Accessed on 26 July 2024.
- Cinner, Joshua E.; Adger, W. Neil; Allison, Edward H.; Barnes, Michele L.; Brown, Katrina; Cohen, Philippa J.; Gelcich, Stefan; Hicks, Christina C.; Hughes, Terry P.; Lau, Jacqueline; Marshall, Nadine A.; Morrison, Tiffany H. (2018). Building adaptive capacity to climate change in tropical coastal communities. *Nature Climate Change*. doi: 10.1038/s41558-017-0065-x.
- Climate-ADAPT (2024). <http://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/knowledge/tools/adaptation-support-tool>. Accessed on 26 July 2024.
- Collier, M.J., Frantzeskaki, N., Connop, S., et al., 2023. An integrated process for planning, delivery, and stewardship of urban nature-based solutions: The Connecting Nature framework. *Nature-Based. Solutions* 3, 100060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2023.100060>.
- Colloff, M.J., Gorddard, R., Abel, N., Locatelli, B., Wyborn, C., Butler, J.R., Dunlop, M., 2021. Adapting transformation and transforming adaptation to climate change using a pathways approach. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 124, 163–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.06.014>.
- Croeser, T., Garrard, G.E., Thomas, F.M., Bekessy, S., 2021. Diagnosing delivery capabilities on a large international NBS project. *Npj Urban. Sustain.* 1, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42949-021-00036-8>.
- Currie-Alder, B., De Souza, K., 2022. Designing Research to Catalyse Climate Action. In: Biswas, A.K., Tortajada, C. (Eds.), *Water Security under Climate Change*. Water Resources Development and Management. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-5493-0_7.
- Daniels, E., Bharwani, S., Swartling, A.G., Vulturius, G., Brandon, K., 2020. Refocusing the climate service lens: Introducing a framework for co-designing transdisciplinary knowledge integration processes to build climate resilience. *Clim. Serv.* 19, 100181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2020.100181>.
- Deubelli, T.M., Mechler, R., 2021. Perspectives on transformational change in climate risk management and adaptation. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16 (5), 053002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abd42d>.
- EEA (2022). Advancing towards climate resilience in Europe: status of reported national adaptation actions in 2021, EEA Report No 11/2022, European Environment Agency <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/advancing-towards-climate-resilience-in-europe> Accessed 26 July 2024.
- EEA (2024). European Climate Risk Assessment (EUCRA). European Environment Agency. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2800/204249>.
- Eisenack, K., Moser, S., Hoffmann, E. et al. (2014). Explaining and overcoming barriers to climate change adaptation. *Nat. Clim. Change* 4, 867–872 (2014). doi: 10.1038/nclimate2350.
- Eisenack, K., Villamayor-Tomas, S., Epstein, G., Kimmich, C., Magliocca, N., Manuel-Navarrete, D., Oberlack, C., Roggero, M., Sietz, D., 2019. Design and quality criteria for archetype analysis. *Ecol. Soc.* 24 (3), 6. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10855-240306>.
- El Amiri, N., Abernethy, P., Spence, N., et al., 2020. Community of practice: an effective mechanism to strengthen capacity in climate change and health. *Can. J. Public. Health* 111, 862–868. <https://doi.org/10.17269/s41997-020-00400-8>.
- European Commission (2019). The European green deal. vol. Communicat. Brussels, Belgium. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b828d165-1c22-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_1&format=PDF. Accessed on 26 July 2024.
- Fedele, G., Donatti, C.I., Harvey, C.A., Hannah, L., Hole, D.G., 2019. Transformative adaptation to climate change for sustainable social-ecological systems. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 101, 116–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.07.001>.
- Fisk, J. M., Harris, P. A., Kuks, S. M. M., Morris, J. C., & Vinke-De Kruijf, J. (2023). Framing Water Infrastructure for Climate Resilience: Governance Dimensions and Challenges. *Public Works Management & Policy*, 1087724X231212556. doi: 10.1177/1087724X231212556.
- Gluckman, P.D., Bardsley, A., Kaiser, M., 2021. Brokerage at the science-policy interface: from conceptual framework to practical guidance. *Humanities Soc. Sci. Commun.* 8 (1), 110. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-00756-3>.
- Haasnoot, M., Kwakkel, J.H., Walker, W.E., Ter Maat, J., 2013. Dynamic adaptive policy pathways: A method for crafting robust decisions for a deeply uncertain world. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 23 (2), 485–498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2012.12.006>.

- Hebinck, A., Diercks, G., von Wirth, T., et al., 2022. An actionable understanding of societal transitions: the X-curve framework. *Sustain. Sci* 17, 1009–1021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01084-w>.
- Hering, J.G., 2016. Do we need “more research” or better implementation through knowledge brokering? *Sustain. Sci.* 11 (2), 363–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-015-0314-8>.
- Hoffmann, S., Deutsch, L., Klein, J.T., O'Rourke, M., 2022. Integrate the integrators! A call for establishing academic careers for integration experts. *Humanit. Soc. Sci. Commun.* 9, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01138-z>.
- Hölscher, K., 2020. Capacities for Transformative Climate Governance: A Conceptual Framework. In: Hölscher, K., Frantzeskaki, N. (Eds.), *Transformative Climate Governance*. Palgrave Studies in Environmental Transformation, Transition and Accountability. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49040-9_2.
- Hölscher, K., Frantzeskaki, F., McPhearson, T., Loorbach, D., 2019. Tales of transforming cities: Transformative climate governance capacities in New York City, U.S. and Rotterdam, Netherlands. *J. Environ. Manage.* 1 (231), 843–857. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.10.043>.
- Hölscher, K., Frantzeskaki, N., Collier, M.J., et al., 2023. Strategies for mainstreaming nature-based solutions in urban governance capacities in ten European cities. *Npj Urban. Sustain.* 3 (54). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42949-023-00134-9>.
- Horcea-Milcu, A.L., Dorresteijn, I., Leventon, J., et al., 2024. Transformative research for sustainability: characteristics, tensions, and moving forward. *Global Sustainability* 7, e14.
- Jordan, A., Huitema, D., Hildén, M., van Asselt, H., Rayner, T.J., Schoenefeld, J.J., Tosun, J., Forster, J., Boasson, E.L., 2015. Emergence of polycentric climate governance and its future prospects. *Nat. Clim. Change* 5, 977–982. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2725>.
- Kemp, L., Xu, C., Depledge, J., Ebi, K.L., Gibbins, G., Kohler, T.A., Rockström, J., Scheffer, M., Schellnhuber, H.J., Steffen, W., Lenton, T.M., 2022. Climate Endgame: Exploring catastrophic climate change scenarios. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 119 (34). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2108146119> e2108146119.
- Klammer, A., Grisold, T., Nguyen, N., Hsu, S., 2024. Organizational unlearning as a process: What we know, what we don't know, what we should know. *Manage. Rev. Quart.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-024-00430-3>.
- Klein, R. J., Adams, K. M., Dzebo, A., Davis, M., & Siebert, C. K. (2017). Advancing climate adaptation practices and solutions: emerging research priorities. Stockholm Environment Institute. Working Paper. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/resrep02838.pdf?acceptTC=true&coverpage=false&addFooter=false> e. Accessed on 26 July 2024.
- Krauss, A., 2019. Unlearning institutional habits: An arts-based perspective on organizational unlearning. *Learn. Organ.* 26 (5), 485–499. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TLO-10-2018-0172>.
- Lang, D.J., Wiek, A., Bergmann, M., et al., 2012. Transdisciplinary research in sustainability science: practice, principles, and challenges. *Sustain. Sci* 7 (Suppl 1), 25–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-011-0149-x>.
- Lonsdale, K., Pringle, P. & Turner, B. 2015. Transformative adaptation: what it is, why it matters & what is needed. UK Climate Impacts Programme, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/293823090_Transformational_Adaptation_what_it_is_w_h_y_it_matters_and_what_is_needed.
- Loorbach, D., Frantzeskaki, N., Avelino, F., 2017. Sustainability transitions research: transforming science and practice for societal change. *Annu. Rev. Env. Resour.* 42, 599–626. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-102014-021340>.
- Lückerath, D., Olfert, A., Milde, K., Ullrich, O., Rome, E., Hutter, G., 2020. Assessment of and tools for improving climate resilience of infrastructures: Towards an ERNCIP Thematic Group. Umweltbundesamt, Dessau-Roßlau.
- Mattern, K., Giannini, V., Downing, C., Gomes, A., Ramieri, E., Karali, E., Capela Lourenço, T., de Jong, F., Coninx, I., Marras, S., Medri, S., Kazmierczak, A. (2018). Sharing adaptation knowledge across Europe: Evidence for the evaluation of Climate-ADAPT. European Topic Centre on Climate Change impacts, Vulnerability and Adaptation (ETC/CCA) Technical paper 2018/2. [doi: 10.25424/CMCC/EVIDENCE_CLIMATE-ADAPT_EVALUATION_2018](https://doi.org/10.25424/CMCC/EVIDENCE_CLIMATE-ADAPT_EVALUATION_2018). Accessed on 26 July 2024.
- McCullagh, D., Beswick, A., Jones, S., McCullough, J., Gault, J., 2023. Transboundary Climate Adaptation and Learning Exchange: Policy and Practice. EPA. Research Report 445.
- McCullagh, D., Langendijk, G.S., Winter, G., Jeuken, A., Cumiskey, L., Medway, P., Camaro, W., 2024a. Climate services: Co-development in Cork City, Ireland. *Soc. Impacts* 4, 100072. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socimp.2024.100072>.
- McCullagh, D., Beswick, A., Jones, S., McCullough, J., Berman, J., Murtagh, E., O'Dwyer, B., Cumiskey, L., O'Mahony, C., 2024b. (2024b) Co-Creating a Framework to Enable Place-Based Climate Adaptation Partnerships: A Practical Guide to Partnership Working. Climate Risk Management, Under Review Nov [unpublished].
- Meharg, S., 2023. Critical change agent characteristics and competencies for ensuring systemic climate adaptation interventions. *Sustain. Sci* 18, 1445–1457. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01250-8>.
- Moser, S.C., Ekstrom, J.A., 2010. A framework to diagnose barriers to climate change adaptation. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 107 (51), 22026–22031. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.100788710>.
- Nightingale, A.J., Gonda, N., Eriksen, S.H., 2022. Affective adaptation = effective transformation? Shifting the politics of climate change adaptation and transformation for the status quo. *Wiley. Interdiscip. Rev. Clim. Chang.* 13 (1), e740.
- Norström, A.V., Cvitanovic, C., Löf, M.F., West, S., Wyborn, C., Balvanera, P., Österblom, H., 2020. Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research. *Nat. Sustainability* 3 (3), 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0448-2>.
- Oberlack, C., 2017. Diagnosing institutional barriers and opportunities for adaptation to climate change. *Mitig. Adapt. Strat. Glob. Chang.* 22 (5), 805–838. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-015-9699-z>.
- Oberlack, C., Sietz, D., Bürgi Bonanomi, E., De Brémond, A., Dell'Angelo, J., Eisenack, K., Ellis, E.C., Epstein, G., Giger, M., Heinemann, A., Kimmich, C., Kok, M.T.J., Manuel-Navarrete, D., Messerli, P., Meyfroidt, P., Václavík, T., Villamayor-Tomas, S., 2019. Archetype analysis in sustainability research: meanings, motivations, and evidence-based policy making. *Ecol. Soc.* 24 (2), 26. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10747-240226>.
- Olsson, P., Folke, C., Berkes, F., 2004. Adaptive Comanagement for Building Resilience in Social– Ecological Systems. *Environ. Manag.* 34, 75–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-003-0101-7>.
- Ostrom, E., 2009. A general framework for analyzing sustainability of social-ecological systems. *Science* 325, 419–422. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1172133>.
- Ostrom, E., 2011. Background on the institutional analysis and development framework. *Policy. Stud. J.* 39 (1), 7–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.2010.00394.x>.
- Owen, G., 2020. What makes climate change adaptation effective? A systematic review of the literature. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 62, 102071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102071>.
- Pedde S., Doblas-Reyes, S., Carter, T.R., Haarsma, R., Jury, M., Burgess, S., Emerton, R., Fronzek, S., Muccione, V. (2024) Chapter 2: Europe in times of change and extremes. In: European climate risk assessment, EEA Report 01/2024, European Environment Agency, Copenhagen, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment>.
- Pedde, S., Kok, K., Hölscher, K., Oberlack, C., Harrison, P.A., Leemans, R., 2019a. Archotyping shared socioeconomic pathways across scales: an application to central Asia and European case studies. *Ecol. Soc.* 24 (4), 30. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11241-240430>.
- Pedde, S., Kok, K., Hölscher, K., Frantzeskaki, N., Holman, I., Dunford, R., Jäger, J., 2019b. Advancing the use of scenarios to understand society's capacity to achieve the 1.5-degree target. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 56, 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2019.03.010>.
- Petzold, J., Hawxwell, T., Jantke, K., et al., 2023. A global assessment of actors and their roles in climate change adaptation. *Nat. Clim. Change.* 13, 1250–1257. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-023-01824-z>.
- Piemontese, L., Neudert, R., Oberlack, C., Pedde, S., Roggero, M., Buchadas, A., Sietz, D., 2022. Validity and validation in archetype analysis: practical assessment framework and guidelines. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 17 (2), 025010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac4f12>.
- Rayner, T., 2023. Adaptation to climate change: EU policy on a Mission towards transformation? *npj Clim. Action* 2, 36. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-023-00068-z>.
- Schröter, K., Schweizer, P.-J., Gräler, B., Cumiskey, L., Bharwani, S., Parviainen, J., Kropf, C., Hakansson, V.W., Drews, M., Irvine, T., Dondi, C., Apel, H., Löhlein, J., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Bagli, S., Huszti, L., Genillard, C., Unguendoli, S., Steinhausen, M., 2024. Invited perspectives: Fostering interoperability of data, models,

- communication and governance for disaster resilience through transdisciplinary knowledge co-production. *Nat. Hazards. Earth. Syst. Sci. Discuss.* [preprint]. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-2024-135> in review.
- Shah, M.A.R., Renaud, F.G., Anderson, C.C., Wild, A., Domeneghetti, A., Polderman, A., Votsis, A., Pulvirenti, B., Basu, B., Thomson, C., Panga, D., Pouta, E., Toth, E., Pilla, F., Sahani, J., Ommer, J., El Zohbi, J., Munro, K., Stefanopoulou, M., Zixuan, W., 2020. A review of hydro-meteorological hazard, vulnerability, and risk assessment frameworks and indicators in the context of nature-based solutions. *Int. J. Disaster. Risk. Reduct.* 50, 101728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101728>.
- Sparkes, E., Totin, E., Werners, S.E., Wise, R.M., Butler, J.R., Vincent, K., 2023. Adaptation pathways to inform policy and practice in the context of development. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 140, 279285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.12.011>.
- Steins, N.A., Veraart, J.A., Klostermann, J.E., Poelman, M., 2021. Combining offshore wind farms, nature conservation and seafood: Lessons from a Dutch community of practice. *Mar. Policy* 126, 104371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104371>.
- Tàbara, J.D., Frantzeskaki, N., Hölscher, K., Pedde, S., Kok, K., Lamperti, F., Berry, P., 2018. Positive tipping points in a rapidly warming world. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 31, 120129.
- TALX (2023). Transboundary adaptation learning Exchange. <https://talx.ie/>. Accessed on 26 July 2024.
- Thaler, T., Attems, M.S., Bonnefond, M., Clarke, D., Gatién-Tournat, A., Gralépois, M., Fuchs, S., 2019. Drivers and barriers of adaptation initiatives—How societal transformation affects natural hazard management and risk mitigation in Europe. *Sci. Total. Environ.* 650, 1073–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.306>.
- Van Oers, L., Feola, G., Runhaar, H., Moors, E., 2023. Unlearning in sustainability transitions: Insight from two Dutch community-supported agriculture farms. *Environ. Innov. Soc. Trans.* 46, 100693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2023.100693>.
- Vinke-de Kruijf, J., Verbrugge, L., Schröter, B., den Haan, R.J., Cortes Arevalo, J., Fliervoet, J., Albert, C., 2022. Knowledge co-production and researcher roles in transdisciplinary environmental management projects. *Sustain. Dev.* 30 (2), 393–405. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2281>.
- Wenger-Trayner, E., Wenger-Trayner, B., Reid, P., Bruderlein, C., 2023. Communities of practice within and across organizations: A guidebook. Accessed on 26 July 2024 Social. Learning. Lab. <https://www.wenger-trayner.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Community-Of-Practice-digital-2-VERSAO.pdf>.
- Werners, S.E., Wise, R.M., Butler, J.R.A., Totin, E., Vincent, K., 2021. Adaptation pathways: A review of approaches and a learning framework. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 116, 266–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.11.003>.
- Wiek, A., Iwaniec, D., 2014. Quality criteria for visions and visioning in sustainability science. *Sustain. Sci.* 9, 497–512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.10.003>.
- Wise, R.M., Butler, J.R.A., Suadnya, W., Puspadi, K., Suharto, I., Skewes, T.D., 2016. How climate compatible are livelihood adaptation strategies and development programs in rural Indonesia? *Clim. Risk. Manag.* 12, 100–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2015.11.001>.